

Applying Earned Value Metrics to Flight Testing¹

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Abstract— The decrease in the defense budget is forcing aviation program managers to actively seek methods of reducing cost and improving the efficiency of the acquisition cycle. Flight testing, a major portion of the non-recurring costs of Research, Development, Test and Evaluation (RDT&E), is an apt candidate for the application of metrics to demonstrate improved efficiency. By appropriately choosing metrics, the program manager, who is the ultimate customer of flight testing, will be equipped with tools that yield an understanding of how flight testing is being conducted, and what progress or value is being achieved. These tools will permit the program manager to successfully and economically manage the risk associated with aviation acquisition. Current acquisition programs are using earned value methods to provide metrics in engineering and manufacturing development. By applying earned value management techniques to flight testing, the program manager can determine what areas of the acquisition program are performing to cost and schedule without requiring additional management methods.

When applying the earned value approach to evaluating flight test programs, the challenge is determining the value associated with each data point. If the metrics are derived properly, a significant amount of useful information will be available to the program managers and the flight test community that may be used to improve test efficiency. A method of attaching value to data that is collected during flight testing is presented in this paper that utilizes the earned value management (EVM) system. The framework used is consistent with the critical technical performance parameters that are to be used to evaluate system (and contractual) performance. Methods of taking credit for value earned are proposed, as well as the potential benefits that can be obtained from using the EVM technique. An example is put forth that incorporates EVM applied to a helicopter hover performance evaluation. The authors assess benefits and pitfalls of using EVM that preserve baseline cost and schedule efficiencies while accounting for unplanned testing and the corresponding increased allocation of resources. The costs associated with applying the EVM approach are discussed, as are methods of tracking value earned. It is shown by way of example that EVM techniques can be successfully applied to flight testing. Finally, recommendations for future work are put forth that

focus on applying this methodology to future programs, as well as validating this model against historical data.

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1. INTRODUCTION

With declining budgets available for defense acquisition, aviation acquisition programs are looking for improved methods of efficiently conducting flight test programs to better manage dwindling fiscal resources. However, the use of metrics in the flight test arena is often overlooked as a valuable management tool because the metrics are inadequate. Traditionally, the primary metric applied to flight testing has been flight hours per month. For example, data points collected during an envelope expansion were plotted in attempts to define the flight envelope. However, other than to define the envelope and develop an intuitive feel for how the test program was progressing, metrics were inadequate and not widely applied. Some programs are currently tracking the number of data points planned vs. the number of data points completed, but the relative value of the data points is not apparent. Avionics and software testing in the flight test phase have not been subject to metrics, increasing the difficulty of process improvement in an area of flight testing that will continue to grow. There are a number of obvious reasons to use metrics in flight testing, primarily in tracking progress towards completion, but also in identifying areas for process improvement. Current acquisition programs are using earned value

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methods to provide metrics in engineering and manufacturing development.

“Earned Value Management (EVM) is the use of an integrated management system that coordinates work scope, schedule, and cost goals and objectively measures progress toward these goals.”[1] By using EVM, the program manager can determine what areas of their acquisition program are performing to cost and schedule. Earned value management and its associated metrics are watched carefully by senior management within the Department of Defense (DOD). An important function of EVM is to provide a detailed picture of cost and schedule variances. The major benefit of EVM is it shows where tasks are diverging from the plan at the lowest task element. That is where the manager can apply motivation, resources or correct a poorly estimated task.

In this paper, we will briefly discuss the traditional EVM technique and its application to a flight test program in order to highlight its usefulness. We will then describe one phase of a flight test program and apply EVM techniques to the presentation of data within that phase. Finally, we will demonstrate how this presentation can provide decision makers an assessment of the earned value of data collected as flight test progresses.

2. ACQUISITION AND THE PROGRAM MANAGER

Acquisition Milestones

In the DOD, the program manager is responsible for shepherding acquisition programs through the life-cycle process from cradle to grave. This life-cycle process is broken down into five phases associated with the following milestone (MS) decision points:

- MS 0 Concept Exploration and Definition
- MS I Demonstration and Validation
- MS II Engineering and Manufacturing Development
- MS III Production and Deployment
- MS IV Operations and Support

While test and evaluation is involved in all phases of the life-cycle, its primary utilization is in providing data to support MS decision points. Two of the significant events leading up to a MS III decision point are successful completion of a developmental test and successful completion of an operational evaluation (OPEVAL) conducted by designated fleet naval squadrons.

Documents and Specifications

In support of the acquisition process, a plethora of documents guide the procurement of a weapons system. Of particular interest to those conducting developmental testing are the specifications under which hardware is procured and the test and evaluation master plan (TEMP), which outlines how testing will be conducted. The TEMP spells out critical technical parameters (CTPs), measures of effectiveness and suitability (MOEs/MOSs), and critical operational issues (COIs) that must be addressed to ascertain integrated system performance. Conversely, fleet personnel conducting OPEVAL, are concerned with the thresholds for MOEs, MOSs and COIs that are set forth in the operational requirements document (ORD).

Typical TEMP objectives include:

Maximum Gross Weight	Maximum Range
Maximum Airspeed	Cruise Airspeed
Climb Performance	Airspeed vs. G Envelope
Hover Performance	Minimum Takeoff Speed

Typical MOE/MOSs and COIs include:

MOE/MOSs:	COIs:
Mission Radius	Mission Planning
Mission Range	Navigation
Inter-operability	Survivability
Internal Payload	Weapons Employment
Troops Carried	Targeting

Management Challenges

The difficulty for the program manager in these life-cycle phases is to manage cost, schedule, and performance to complete OPEVAL successfully. The DOD mandates the use of EVM for all research, development, test, and evaluation contracts with a value of \$70 million or more and procurement contracts with a value of \$300 million or more [2]. The metrics of EVM provide some measure of progress along the program baseline in terms of cost and schedule, however they provide little insight into the technical risk of failing OPEVAL. What the program manager needs is useful metrics aside from those in the TEMP that will predict a measure of performance toward MOEs, MOSs, and COIs. If these metrics are cast in the framework of earned value, then the value associated with obtaining technical data required to support OPEVAL and developmental test decisions can be used to evaluate the risk of completing these milestones successfully. Armed with this information, resources (funds, assets, and personnel) can be properly applied to mitigate this risk.

3. TRADITIONAL EARNED VALUE METHODS

EVM is a method of systematically measuring progress toward the goal of project completion. Simply measuring

money spent and work completed as measures of progress does not sufficiently answer the question; is the project on track? The following EVM terms are defined [3]:

- BCWS** Budgeted Cost for Work Scheduled. The project baseline or plan that encompasses all work packages, funding, and scheduling.
- BCWP** Budgeted Cost for Work Performed. The actual performance or earned value of the work performed.
- ACWP** Actual Cost of Work Performed. The actual project cost as opposed to the projected cost.
- BAC** Budget at Completion. The total cost of all of the budgeted plans.
- EAC** Estimate at Completion. The forecast of the actual total cost at completion based on the BCWS and the ACWP to date.

Figure 1 shows a cumulative plan/status display for a typical project. In this presentation, project status in terms of cost and schedule is clearly seen. In this example, the project is behind schedule (BCWP lower than BCWS) and over budget (ACWP higher than BCWP).

It is well documented that the trends in schedule and cost are established as an indicator for the entire program, if the project is more than 15% complete [1]. After this point budget overruns cannot generally be recovered and schedule slippage tends to grow rather than shrink. The two key performance indices that may be calculated from data presented in the EVM format are cost and schedule efficiencies or cost performance index (CPI) and schedule performance index (SPI):

$$\text{Cost Efficiency} \quad \text{CPI} = \frac{\text{BCWP}}{\text{ACWP}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Schedule Efficiency} \quad \text{SPI} = \frac{\text{BCWP}}{\text{BCWS}} \quad (2)$$

Where CPI or SPI > 1.0 is favorable and < 1.0 is unfavorable.

These indices are aggressively tracked by senior managers within the DOD. In the current budget environment, if CPI or SPI are unfavorable at early milestones in a program, it is at risk of cancellation or additional oversight.

Earned value metrics are extremely useful in projecting costs, schedule and performance to the planned project baseline. In our case, these indices assist in evaluating the efficiency of the flight test program. However, when the baseline changes as a result of unforeseen technical difficulties, management against the baseline yields skewed results. These indicators still provide insight into likely cost and schedule overruns, but will not indicate the ability of the

Figure 1 EVM Cumulative Plan/Status Display²

project team to successfully complete OPEVAL. What the program manager needs is a method of computing the value of data collected during flight test, and its value towards validating TEMP and ORD metrics.

Benefits

There are real benefits that can be gained by the use of earned value metrics in a flight test program. As discussed earlier, schedule adjustments may fall out of the detailed planning efforts needed to establish metrics. Moreover, attention can more easily be focused on areas that are falling behind schedule and above cost, because these cost and schedule variances indicate risk.

The lessons learned in flight testing are not available in an easily accessible format. The gray beard approach to risk management is currently the standard, in which the most experienced personnel are brought together to discuss the risk and generate a solution. Once these more seasoned personnel retire, that experience is lost. The metrics that will be available from EVM should provide significant insight to lessons learned for future flight test efforts. The following questions are only a sample of what can be learned from flight testing if the metrics are collected in a reproducible fashion:

- Was enough test time allotted for test evolutions?
- Were maintenance delays and inspections planned correctly?
- What were the maintenance delays?

² As taken from [3]

- Was some maintenance less intensive than anticipated?
- Was the use of simulation effective?
- Were there specific times during the year that showed an improved productivity?
- Was the use of military maintainers effective in preparation for operational test?
- Was enough time planned for executive demonstration flights?

The benefits for future programs alone should make the effort needed in the planning stages of the flight test program well worth the cost. As more programs use EVM, more information on planning will become available and increasingly accurate planning will result. All of this assumes that programs are willing to share the information. If applied at the outset, the payback on current flight test programs will be worth the effort. Addressing areas that were found problematic during developmental testing will improve the weapon systems performance during OPEVAL. If one area of testing is progressing better than planned, adjustments can be made to cover a variance in a different test area that is falling behind.

4. DEFINING THE WORK PACKAGE

Traditional EVM techniques strive to create work packages at the lowest possible level in order to make the package as distinct and short as possible. If this is done properly, work packages should be finite enough to illustrate progress, yet detailed enough to provide management insight into problems that may occur. For longer duration work packages, the package should be subdivided into discrete value milestones that allow objective measurement of work performed.

In our flight test example, breaking work packages down by major test phase such as envelope expansion, load surveys, and weapons evaluations, provides insufficient detail to provide much insight into progress. Similarly, tracking progress by flight hour, while useful for evaluating total costs, does not provide the necessary information to easily see if the program is on track. One solution to this problem is to consider major test phases as roll-ups of several work packages that break down the phase into logical groupings of test points. For instance, during envelope expansion several major areas of flight will be examined: maximum gross weight takeoff, level flight, climbs and descents, etc. Within these sub-groups are additional levels of granularity such as center of gravity locations and gross weights. This is too much detail for management reporting, but may be necessary to derive the best value from the metrics. Flight hours are still be tracked; however, they are not used as indicators of performance within a work package, but are used to separate flight costs from other expenses. In our example, the data related to hover performance that are gathered during envelope expansion, loads and vibrations, weapons accuracy, structural demonstration, etc. are

considered to be part of the hover performance work package.

5. HOVER PERFORMANCE EXAMPLE

Hover performance is an essential performance parameter for helicopters. Mission requirements identify performance parameters that the OPEVAL tester will evaluate. The mission requirements define a maximum level-takeoff gross weight, high altitude hover capability, hot day hover performance, shipboard takeoff and landing, weapons delivery accuracy, and associated handling qualities. To put it simply, hover performance is based on power available, power required and atmospheric conditions. For the purposes of this paper, we will group hover flying qualities and performance together as hover performance. In the application of EVM to hover performance, many associated areas of flight test can provide earned value in evaluating the hover performance metric. Insight into hover performance can be gained from the following flight test areas:

1. Envelope Expansion
2. Non-Firing Load Survey
3. Non-Firing Vibration Survey
4. Firing Loads and Vibrations
5. Weapons Accuracy
6. Structural Demonstration
7. Air Combat Maneuvering
8. Handling Qualities
9. Performance and Height Velocity Demonstrations at Sea Level and at High Altitude
10. Sea Trials

The performance and height velocity demonstrations, handling qualities and sea trials portions of the test program will have significant portions of the testing directly related to hover performance. These areas will earn correspondingly more value for the hover performance metric and have a high cost since hover performance is a specific goal of the testing. Some knowledge and earned value from the other areas of testing listed above can be gained at a low cost. Hover performance data collection is a fallout of each flight, since some performance data can be gathered from each takeoff and landing, even though the hover data are not a primary objective of these flight tests. The amount of information or earned value that can be learned from each test area is presented graphically in Figure 2.

In the sample test program, it is expected that 7% of the information necessary to determine if the aircraft capabilities are sufficient to meet the hover performance requirements will be available upon the completion of the envelope expansion tests. This early look at the hover performance will provide insight on the need for any aircraft modifications that may improve performance. If the schedule is correlated with the earned value presentation, an earned value curve (BCWP) can be generated, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Percentage Value of Hover Data

Figure 3. Budgeted Cost for Work Performed - Hover

Combining the schedule and cost associated with collecting the flight test information will produce the budgeted cost for work scheduled (BCWS) curve, as shown in Figure 4. These are the costs budgeted for the test events. For example, the primary purpose of envelope expansion is to define the flight envelope of the aircraft, not to determine hover performance. Therefore, of the total cost for envelope expansion tests, only 7% was budgeted for hover performance. The slope of the curve increases dramatically during the performance and height-velocity demonstrations at sea level and high altitude and sea trials, since a significant portion of these tests are related to the hover performance capabilities of the aircraft.

In the model flight test program developed for this paper, a number of options become apparent. Schedule adjustments might be used to provide insight to the performance of high risk areas or to get an earlier look at a specific mission area. In our example, sea trials, high altitude performance, and the height velocity demonstration will ultimately prove the hover performance capabilities of the aircraft. The timing of sea trials and the high altitude demonstrations is not conducive to implementing any necessary modifications to the aircraft in sufficient time for operational test. It would be prudent to modify the test schedule (if other factors are conducive) to provide more information on the hover performance (or earned value) earlier in the schedule.

6. APPLYING OF THE ACTUAL COST OF WORK PERFORMED

For the model flight test program, an actual cost of work performed (ACWP) curve has been plotted on the earned value chart shown in Figure 5. The actual cost is below the budgeted cost of testing for hover performance. This indicates that the program is ahead of schedule in dollars, and the CPI and SPI are greater than one.

7. BASELINE MANAGEMENT

Figure 4. Budgeted Cost for Flight Test Work Scheduled

When using EVM, all progress is measured against the baseline. If sufficient planning is performed up front with realistic estimates, then the baseline is an effective tool to measure progress. If a re-baselining becomes necessary, then the management team will carry the burden of all prior inefficiencies in the CPI and SPI as indicators of performance. However, this is not so easily applied to the flight test environment. By its very nature, flight testing is designed to uncover problems. Solutions to these problems are often iterative, and require indeterminate resources for their resolution. Since they are unforeseen, planning for them is often inaccurate. The project team will strive to build contingencies into the schedule for high risk data points, however, predicting resources necessary to resolve complex technical difficulties relating to flight test is not a science. When these problems do arise, all of the careful planning of resources is often redirected towards overcoming the technical hurdle. *In these situations, the CPI and SPI indices will show unfavorable results that do not indicate flight test inefficiency.*

To prevent misinterpretation of the indices, the customer and the flight test team must agree up-front that when unforeseen problems arise, the program will be re-baselined by increasing BCWP by the actual costs of completing the offending work package. This method provides a solution but has two drawbacks. First, the increase in ACWP must be multiplied by the current efficiency index to produce a BCWP that maintains the ratio. Second, the indices become harder to influence if flight test efficiencies are realized, because they are small portions of a now larger total. A plot of the actual cost of flight test work performed would now look like that shown in Figure 6, with discontinuities where the re-baselining took place.

Figure 5. Actual Cost of Flight Test Work Performed

Figure 6. Actual Cost of Flight Test Work Performed After Re-baselining

8. COSTS ASSOCIATED WITH THE USE OF EARNED VALUE METRICS

The cost of providing earned value metrics to the program manager should be considered. Identifying what parameters should be tracked and how the value is determined logically belongs to the flight test community, however the program will ultimately bear this cost. To be efficient, earned value should be applied during the flight test planning. Setting up the process for tracking the data also needs to be considered during the initial phases of test planning. A database that can track and compare the flight test data collected and attach an earned value needs to be defined. To be more efficient, current flight test planning efforts are applying data from one area to another, where possible. For example, hover performance data will be collected on each envelope expansion takeoff and landing for possible use in handling qualities, hover performance, and dynamic interface. Tracking the cost of EVM during the test phase should not be a significant (and probably negligible when compared to the cost of the flight test program). Costs will occur in the reporting of earned value data and software needed to collate all flight test areas into one set of earned value data for flight test or even for the overall program. An analysis of the cost and benefits of the program-wide earned value management process is presented in reference [4].

9. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

We have identified a method of presenting flight test data that provides early indicators of technical performance, which may be used as metrics to evaluate program success. In our example, the actual value of the data collected was somewhat arbitrary because the primary purpose of this discussion was to develop and present the format. It is important to consider that we have only examined one portion of the model flight test program. To provide a meaningful picture to program management, the hover performance data would need to be integrated with the remaining test objectives and critical performance parameters. This will provide a complete picture of applying earned value metrics to flight testing.

Recommendations for future work include the following:

1. Develop rigorous methods for establishing the value of flight test data at each phase of testing.
2. Validate the data presentation model against the historical data from an actual flight test program.
3. Develop and link software tools to provide an easy method for incorporating data in a timely fashion.

EVM can be adopted by the RDT&E community to better evaluate the risk and cost associated with aviation acquisition programs. While this paper only presented an EVM framework for a hover performance evaluation, the methodology is applicable to all phases of flight testing. If

the program manager and flight test team to identify and agree upon the specific metrics that will be tracked early in the flight test planning process, EVM will provide a truly effective management tool for aircraft acquisition.

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